

CHATBOT APPLICATION AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effectiveness of a chatbot application in enhancing Grade 8 learners' performance in Physics at San Agustin National High School, Sagbayan District, Bohol, for the school year 2022-2023. A quasi-experimental design was employed, with the experimental group using the chatbot application and the control group receiving traditional instruction. Pre-tests and post-tests assessed performance improvements. The results revealed that while the traditional method showed modest improvements—shifting learners from the "developing" category to "approaching proficient" and "proficient"—the chatbot intervention led to substantial gains. The experimental group demonstrated significant progress, achieving higher categories such as "advanced" and "proficient." Statistical analysis confirmed a significant difference favoring the chatbot group in post-test performance and mean gain scores. These findings suggest that the chatbot application effectively enhanced learners' performance in Physics compared to traditional methods. The study underscores the potential of integrating educational chatbots to address learning challenges and improve academic outcomes.

Keywords: *Chatbot, Educational Technology, Learning Outcomes, Physics Instruction, Technology Integration*

INTRODUCTION

Educational technology encompasses various emerging tools designed to enhance teaching and learning processes. Chatbot applications represent a promising

yet underutilized technology in academic contexts. A chatbot is a programmed application embedded within platforms like messaging services or web applications, designed to automate responses to user inquiries by sending predefined messages. Accessible via mobile phones or other devices, chatbots offer a free, convenient way for users to interact with educational content, provided they are not Globe or TM subscribers, as the messaging services are free for Smart, TalknTxt, and Sun subscribers.

Educational chatbots are specifically designed to leverage this technology to improve academic outcomes. While the integration of chatbots in commercial settings has gained traction due to their effectiveness in customer interactions—Luo et al. (2019) found that chatbots are four times more effective than inexperienced workers in driving customer purchases—its potential in education remains relatively unexplored. Kumar (2021) highlighted that educational chatbots could enhance learning performance and teamwork, suggesting significant benefits for their application in educational settings.

Recent educational performance metrics underscore the need for such technological advancements. The 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) reported that the Philippines scored 357 in science, below the average of participating OECD countries as cited (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024). Furthermore, the Philippines' position dropped to 51st out of 132 countries in the Global Innovation Index, a decline from its improving trajectory since 2014 (Arayata, 2021). This decline is reflected in the struggles faced in science education, including Physics, which remains a concern for many schools (Nava & Camarao, 2017) and is exacerbated by limited instructional materials (Orleans, 2007).

To address these challenges, the present study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a chatbot application in improving academic performance in Physics. The chatbot, delivered through a messenger application, seeks to provide high-quality, accessible learning materials anytime and anywhere. By integrating chatbot technology into Physics instruction, this study hopes to offer a modern solution to the issues of accessibility and engagement in learning.

The research is grounded in several theoretical frameworks. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), proposed by Davis (1989), emphasizes that the perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU) of a technology are crucial for its acceptance and utilization. The chatbot intervention aims to enhance physics learning by being useful, user-friendly, and accessible via widely used mobile platforms. The Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) further supports this approach by underscoring the need for integrating technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge in educational technology applications.

The SMAR model (Puentedura, 2014) also provides a structured approach to technology integration, encompassing Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition. This model suggests that technology should replace existing practices, enhance and modify activities, and redefine learning experiences. The chatbot

application aligns with these phases by substituting traditional learning materials, augmenting accessibility, modifying traditional activities with interactive features, and redefining student-teacher interactions.

The International Union of Pure and Applied Physics (IUPAP, 1999) and Ellermeijer & Tran (2019) highlight the importance of leveraging technology in education. They stress the role of Physics in driving technological advancement and the potential of technology to make learning more relevant and engaging. Studies by Corpuz (2017) and Delos Santos et al. (2020) emphasize the need for innovative solutions to address learning challenges and engage students.

In conclusion, this study seeks to explore the effectiveness of chatbot technology in enhancing Physics education using a framework grounded in TAM, TPACK, and the SMAR model. By providing students with accessible and engaging learning resources, this research aims to contribute to improving educational outcomes and addressing the challenges faced in Physics instruction.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using a chatbot application via messenger in enhancing the performance of Grade 8 learners in Physics at San Agustin National High School, Sagbayan District, Bohol, for the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, this seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of the control group using the traditional method of delivering instruction in the:
 - 1.1. Pretest; and
 - 1.2. Posttest?
2. What is the performance of the Experimental Group using the chatbot application in delivering instruction in the:
 - 2.1. Pretest; and
 - 2.2. Posttest?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the Control group and the Experimental Group?
4. Is there a mean gain performance in the posttest between the control and experimental groups?

METHODOLOGY

This succeeding discussion deals with the research design, subjects of this investigation, research environment, data gathering procedure, the instrument used, and the statistical technique employed in testing the data.

Research Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design. The researcher used a researcher-made test to evaluate the performance of two groups of respondents through pre-tests and post-tests. Purposive sampling was utilized to select respondents for the experimental group based on the minimum requirement of having access to gadgets that could use messenger applications. The same sampling method was applied to the control group to ensure that the mental capabilities of both groups were comparable. Data collected were analyzed using a t-test and mean to determine the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing the learners' performance in Physics.

Research Environment

The research locale for this study was the learners from two selected Grade 8 sections at San Agustin National High School in San Agustin, Sagbayan, Bohol. Sagbayan, located in the interior part of Bohol, is 2.4 km from the municipality center. The largest school in the municipality had an enrollment of 1,758 students, with 55 teaching staff and 6 non-teaching staff for the 2022-2023 school year. San Agustin National High School was chosen due to its large student population, which allowed the appropriate respondents to be selected for the study.

Research Participants

The study's respondents were Grade 8 learners from San Agustin National High School, divided into two groups. Grade 8 learners were selected due to their enrollment in a Physics curriculum relevant to the study's topic. Group A, the control group, consisted of 48 learners, while Group B, the experimental group, had the same number. These sections were chosen because their average performance on a diagnostic test conducted during the first week of Quarter 1 for the 2022-2023 school year was nearly identical. Group A had an average score of 84.43, and Group B had an average score of 84.12. Group B was selected as the experimental group due to its slightly lower average performance and because all learners in this group had Android phones, meeting the minimum requirement for implementing the intervention.

Research Instrument

To gather the necessary information, the researcher used a researcher-made test. Three different San Agustin National High School science teachers reviewed and validated this test. Additionally, to ensure quality, the test was pilot tested with 30 random Grade 8 students at the school who were not part of the study's direct respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

Gathering of Data. The researcher sought and obtained permission from the district supervisor of Sagbayan and the principal of San Agustin National High School to conduct the research, distribute the researcher-made test, and implement the

intervention. Upon receiving approval, the researcher first contextualized common Physics topics for inclusion in the chatbot intervention. The final draft of these contextualized learning materials was then developed into a chatbot application. After creating the chatbot intervention, the researcher conducted an orientation for the study's participants.

Table 1. Implementation Activities.

DAYS	CONTROL GROUP	EXPERIMENTAL GROUP
Week 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation of the direct participants of the study • Distribution of parents' consent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation of the direct participants of the study • Distribution of parents' consent
Week 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieval of parents' consent • Conduct of Pre-Test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieval of parents' consent • Conduct of Pre-Tests
Week 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribution of contextualized printed learning materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation & demonstration on how to access and use the Chatbot Intervention • Distribution of available links to the Chatbot Application
Week 4 - 11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow-up and monitoring of the participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow-up and monitoring of the participants
Week 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct Post-Test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct Post-Tests

Table 1 outlines the overall activities conducted during the implementation of the study. In the first week, the researcher held an orientation for both groups to explain the study's purpose and the respondents' rights and welfare. During this orientation, informed consent forms were distributed. Due to the pandemic, health protocols were followed, with only 20 students allowed per classroom. The orientation was conducted in two sessions for each group to ensure adherence to safety measures. Respondents were informed that their participation was voluntary, their privacy would be protected, and all data would be destroyed after the study.

In the second week, the researcher collected informed consent from parents and administered a pre-test to both groups. The following week, contextualized learning materials were distributed to the control group. The experimental group received an orientation and demonstration on accessing and using the chatbot application. After confirming that participants understood how to use the chatbot, links to the application were sent to the experimental group. The content provided through the chatbot was the same as the printed materials given to the control group, differing only in the method of access—digital for the experimental group and printed for the control group.

Classes were conducted for both groups from the fourth to the eleventh week, with the researcher ensuring that the same topics were covered simultaneously. In the experimental group, the researcher monitored the use of the chatbot application, while in the control group, the use of printed materials was overseen. The researcher addressed technical issues for the experimental group and ensured that all control group participants received their printed materials.

After all topics were covered, the researcher administered a post-test to assess the performance of both groups. To ensure validity, the test items were re-shuffled. Data were collected immediately after the post-test, and responses were tallied, collated, tabulated, and analyzed according to the study's objectives.

Data Analysis

To identify the performance of the two groups of respondents, the percentage was used:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where: % = Percent
f = Frequency
N = Number of cas

The computed percentage will be interpreted using the following grading scale:

Grading Scale	Description
36 and above	Advance
34 - 35	Proficient
32 - 33	Approaching Proficient
30 - 31	Developing 29
and below	Beginning

To determine the level of interest of the experimental group in learning physics using a chatbot, the weighted mean of the responses to the survey questionnaire will be used.

$$W = \frac{\sum fw}{\sum f}$$

Where:

Wm = weighted mean

\sum = Summation

f = frequency of the respondents who responded on the given scale

w = weight of the category specified in the scale

To identify the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the control and experimental groups, the paired t-test was used:

Paired t-test formula:

$$t = \frac{\sum D}{\sqrt{[N(\sum D^2) - (\sum D)^2] / (N - 1)}}$$

Where:

- t = t-value
- D = difference between the two samples (A-B)
- N = sample size

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the study's data. It is divided into four sections: the first section details the performance of the control group, which used the traditional method; the second section covers the performance of the experimental group, which used the chatbot intervention; the third section compares the performance between the control and experimental groups; and the fourth section examines the differences in mean gain between the two groups.

Table 2. Performance of the control group using the traditional method.

Category	Score	Pretest		Posttest	
		f	%	f	%
Advanced	36 - 40	-	-	-	-
Proficient	34 - 35	-	-	12	25
Approaching Proficient	32 - 33	8	17	6	12.5
Developing	30 - 31	35	73	18	37.5
Beginning	< 30	5	10	12	25
	Total	48	100	48	100

Table 2 shows the pretest and posttest performance of the control group using the traditional instruction method. In the pretest, 35 respondents, or 73%, scored between 30 and 31, placing them in the developing category, while 5 respondents, or 10%, were in the beginning category. This result indicated that many respondents were still at the developing stage of learning Physics before the study was implemented, and in the post-test, 18 respondents, or 37.5%, remained in the developing category. In contrast, another 37.5% moved to the approaching proficient and proficient categories. This slight increase in performance suggests that the traditional method of instruction effectively improved the learners' performance in Physics.

Table 3. Performance of the experimental group using the chatbot intervention.

Category	Score	Pretest		Posttest	
		f	%	f	%
Advanced	36 - 40	-	-	5	11
Proficient	34 - 35	-	-	15	31
Approaching Proficient	32 - 33	10	21	25	52
Developing	30 - 31	29	60	3	6
Beginning	< 30	9	19	-	-
	Total	48	100	48	100

Table 3 shows the experimental group's performance exposed to the chatbot application. In the pre-test, 29 respondents, or 60%, scored between 30 and 31, placing them in the developing category, while 10 respondents, or 21%, were in the approaching proficient category. Similar to the control group, the pre-test results in the experimental group were low.

In the post-test, the experimental group's performance improved significantly. The results showed 11% in the advanced category, 31% in the proficient category, and 52% in the approaching proficient category. This improvement indicates that exposure to the chatbot intervention enhanced the experimental group's performance in Physics.

The findings suggest that the chatbot intervention was effective in increasing the learners' scores. This supports Tumaneng's (2012) assertion that ICT integration should focus on learning with ICT tools rather than just the technology itself. The ease of using the chatbot and learners' familiarity with mobile phones contributed to this improvement. Additionally, as noted by Habibi (2014), students lacking resources often lose interest and motivation. The chatbot intervention addressed issues related to the availability of learning materials, helping students achieve better performance in Physics.

Table 4. The significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the Control group and the Experimental group.

Variables	Mean ± SD	Computed t-value	P-value	Interpretation

Pretest between Control & Experimental Group	12.6±3.6 13.0±4.2	-0.64	0.52	Not Significant
Posttest between Control & Experimental Group	15.83±8.3 23.6±5.7	-5.94	0.0000032	Significant
Pre & posttest Control Group	12.6±3.6 15.8±8.3	-3.08	0.003	Significant
Pre & Posttest Experimental Group	13.0±4.2 23.6±5.7	-12.01	0.000016	Significant

Table 4 summarizes the differences between the pre-test and post-test results of the control and experimental groups. The t-test results indicated that the pre-test t-value of -0.64 was less than the p-value of 0.52, showing no statistically significant difference between the pre-test performances of the control and experimental groups. In contrast, the post-test results revealed a p-value of 0.0000032, indicating a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

These findings suggest that the two groups' performance was similar before the intervention, confirming their appropriateness for the study. However, the significant difference in post-test results indicates that the experimental group performed better after using the chatbot application. This suggests that the chatbot intervention effectively improved the respondents' performance in Physics.

Table 5. Mean gain performance of the control and experimental groups.

Variables	Mean of pretest	Mean of posttest	Mean gain
Control Group	12.58	15.83	3.25
Experimental Group	12.87	23.53	10.66

Table 5 presents the respondents' mean performance gains after the intervention. The control group had a mean gain of 3.25, while the experimental group achieved a mean gain of 10.66. This result indicates that the experimental group, which used the chatbot intervention, outperformed the control group, which used the traditional teaching method. Overall, the findings suggest that the chatbot intervention was more effective in enhancing learners' performance in Physics than the traditional method.

Higgins (2003) emphasized that the goal of integrating ICT into education is to improve teaching effectiveness and student learning. The results of this study support the notion that using chatbot technology significantly enhances learning outcomes in Physics, demonstrating the benefits of ICT integration in education.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The analysis of the data yielded the following findings:

1. In the Control group using the traditional method of delivering instruction, the pre-test result disclosed that prior to the study's implementation, 73% of the learners scored in the *developing category*, while after the observation period, the post-test showed that the learners scored in the *approaching proficient (25%)* and *proficient (12.5%)* categories. It can be inferred that the traditional method of delivering instruction can slightly increase the learners' performance in Physics.
2. In the experimental group using the Chatbot application in delivering instruction, the pre-test showed that 60% scored at *developing* and 21% at *approaching proficient* categories. In the post-test, the experimental group improved to higher categories: 11% in the *advanced* category, 31% in the *proficient*, and 52% in the *approaching proficient* categories. The result revealed that a significant number of respondents attained the performance of "approaching proficient" after implementing the chatbot intervention. It can be inferred that the chatbot intervention enhances the performance of the learners of the experimental group in learning Physics.
3. There was no significant difference in the pre-test results between the control and experimental groups; however, a significant difference was observed in the post-tests. This implies that after the study was implemented, the performance of the control and experimental groups differed in favor of the group treated with the Chatbot intervention.
4. The study's results revealed that each group of respondents performed well on mean gain. However, the mean gain score of the experimental group was much higher than that of the control group. This can be inferred from the fact that the experimental group performed better on learning physics using the chatbot application than the control group using the traditional method of delivering instruction.

Conclusions

The findings indicate that while the traditional method of instruction led to a slight improvement in Physics performance, the Chatbot intervention significantly enhanced learner outcomes. The control group showed some progress, with a shift from "developing" to "approaching proficient" and "proficient" categories. In contrast, the experimental group demonstrated substantial gains, with notable improvements in higher performance categories such as "advanced" and "proficient" after using the Chatbot. The significant difference in post-test results and the higher mean gain of the experimental group confirm that the Chatbot application was more effective in improving Physics performance than the traditional method.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion derived from the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

1. Expand Use of Chatbot Technology

Schools should consider incorporating chatbot applications into their teaching strategies, especially for subjects like Physics. The effectiveness of the chatbot intervention in this study suggests that it can significantly enhance learners' understanding and performance. Expanding the use of this technology could provide similar benefits across various subjects.

2. Provide Training for Teachers

To maximize the benefits of digital tools like chatbots, teachers should receive training on integrating such technologies into their curricula. Professional development programs can equip educators with the skills to effectively use and manage chatbot applications, ensuring they can support and enhance student learning.

3. Conduct Further Research

Additional studies should be conducted to explore the effectiveness of chatbots in different educational contexts and subjects. Research could also investigate the long-term impact of chatbot interventions on student learning and engagement, as well as their potential to address diverse learning needs.

4. Enhance Technical Support

Schools should ensure that adequate technical support is available for both students and teachers when implementing chatbot interventions. Addressing technical issues promptly can help maintain the effectiveness of the tool and ensure a smooth learning experience for students.

5. Incorporate Student Feedback

Collect and analyze feedback from students using chatbot applications to continually improve the intervention. Understanding students' experiences and challenges with the technology can provide valuable insights for refining and optimizing its use in future educational settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

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